

Sustainable Development Goals 8&9: Challenges and Policy Options of Nigeria Government

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was initiated by the United Nations as a follow up to Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) which has elapsed without much success. Seventeen goals made up the sustainable development goals but this paper paid attention to Goals 8&9 because of its potentials to bring accelerated development to Nigeria. Goal 8 is about promoting sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all. Goal 9 is to build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation. The crux of the paper was finding out the challenges bedeviling the realization of the goals and proffering some policy options that will help the state bureaucracy focus and achieve purposeful development. In achieving that, data was obtained from secondary sources. Descriptive and content analytical methods of analysis were used in the research. It was discovered that SDGs 8 & 9 are confronted by a quartet of challenges which include insecurity, corona virus pandemic, insufficient funding and corruption. The paper proposed some policies as mitigating factors. They include that government should bring about the policy of incentive education that will later open the floodgates of employment; that special anti-corruption courts or tribunals should be created to deal with only corruption cases quickly; that government should map out more funds (about 26% of the country's annual budget) to the implementation of SDGs; and that government should establish community policing, state police, and vigilante groups, as state policies that can tackle the spate of insecurities in Nigeria. With these policies, goals of SDGs 8 & 9 and indeed other goals of the sustainable development program will be met before the target date of 2023.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Insecurity, Corona Virus, Millennium Development Goals (MDGs)

Introduction

The world adopted the sustainable development goals (SDGs) as an aftermath of the failure of the earlier adopted millennium development goals (MDGs). Millennium development goals were initiated by World leaders under the UN Millennium Declaration in year 2000. Under this declaration, nations of the world were committed to a global challenge aimed at reducing extreme poverty and other debilitating factors by the year 2015 (Olaribe& Taylor Robinson, 2016).

By 2015, many third world countries including Nigeria have not made notable progress or success of those bold goals. Olaribe& Taylor Robinson (2016) attributed this failure to a variety of reasons including bureaucracy, poor resource management and incessant industrial actions by workers, insecurity heightened by Boko Haram insurgency in the North of Nigeria and Kidnappings in the south. In an end-report of the implementation of Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) by the office of the Senior Special Assistant to the President of Nigeria on Millennium Development Goals, it was reported that Nigeria experienced a bag of mixed results. While there were progress and improvement in areas like reduction of maternal and child mortality, eradication of polio, reduction in the spread of malaria and HIV/AIDS and achievement of higher net enrolment in basic education and gender parity in the primary school, there were challenges in areas like sanitation, climate change and other environmental challenges such as pollution, desertification, erosion and flooding, etc. (MDG Report, 2015).

Based on these MDGs failures and challenges in Nigeria, a new development framework the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was adopted to help lift citizens out of poverty, deprivation and environmental disasters. There are seventeen sustainable development goals adopted by the United Nations. However, this paper will dwell on goals 8 & 9 which are the ones that will bring accelerated development to Nigeria and they include: To promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all and; to build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation. The target for the achievement of these goals is year 2030. The paper will x-ray the challenges of goals 8 & 9 and proffers policy options in a bid to help the state bureaucracy focus and achieve purposeful development this time around.

Literature Review

Development

Development may be seen as advancement in political, economic and socio-cultural lives of the people as a result of advancement in science and technology (Chukwuka, 2014). Ogbe (2011) sees it as increased capacity, greater effectiveness and efficiency, improved technology, knowledge, initiative and disposition which people acquired overtime. Development involves increase and improvement in social and economic overheads especially of a country. At the heart of development is improvement in the standard of living of the people and building of their capacity to command best quality of life. According to Seers (1964) the question to ask about a country's development are therefore: What has been happening to poverty? What has been happening to unemployment? What has been happening to inequality? If all three of these have declined from high level, then beyond doubt this have been a period of development for the country concerned. If one or two of these central problems have been growing worse, especially if all three have, it would be strange to call the result 'development', even if per capita income declined. From Dudley Seers analysis, it can be said of Nigeria that the three central problems mentioned above is growing rapidly, as the country is the world headquarter for poverty overtaking India. Bukola (2018) noted that Nigeria has overtaken India as a country with the largest number of people living in extreme poverty, with an estimated 87 million Nigerians, or around half of the country population, thought to be living on less than \$1.90 a day. The unemployment situation is alarming, as youths are not gainfully employed after graduation. UNDP (2021) lamented that, an estimated 172 million people worldwide were without work in 2018- an unemployment rate of 5% while in Nigeria the unemployment rate currently is 7.96% while Simona (2021) observed that in 2021, the unemployment rate in Nigeria is estimated to reach 32.5 percent. This figure is projected to increase further in 2022. Chronological data show that the unemployment rate in Nigeria rose constantly in the past years.

Characteristic	Unemployment rate
2020	7.96%
2019	8.1%
2018	8.24%
2017	8.39%
2016	7.06%
2015	4.31%
2014	4.56%
2013	3.7%
2012	3.74%
2011	3.77%
2010	3.77%
2009	3.72%
2008	3.54%

Source: Aaron (2012)

This is a clear indication that Nigeria is still yet to move away from the path of underdevelopment. Often than not people mistake development for good road, good hospital, quality education, stable power supply amongst others but all these even though vital are infrastructural development which are intangible indicators of development.

Development implies to cause to grow or expand, to realize what was potential to change or progress. Development therefore is a change, improvement, or progress in the living condition of people; an improvement in the political, economic, social, and cultural institution as well as an advancement in the living standards of the people (Nnamani, 2009). Development can occur as a result of various means including improved technology and increased capacity occasioned through extension of credit facilities. Oguonu (2012) supporting this assertion noted that development is a process whereby government of a country ensures that standard of living of the people and their economic status are improved through various means including the extension of credit facilities to encourage the establishment of small and medium enterprises. This means that development involves two actors, the government and the governed. It connotes cooperation and participation. Government providing the platform for capacity building and the governed taking advantage of the platform to increase their capacities and become effective and efficient. In that vein, Arvind and Everett in Nnamani (2009) stated that development is a widely participatory process of directed social change in society intended to bring about both social and material advancement (in qualities) for majority of the people through their gaining greater control over their environment. Development the authors continue may also mean improvement in the social status of the people; it is absolutely a participatory process leading to growth and social change. The end-product of development is a developed man or woman and their material conditions.

Development was also seen in terms of the structure and growth of the national economy and degrees of development (or underdevelopment) were also often measured in terms of national income. In that line, the two most common indicators of development were per capital income (national income divided by the size of the population) and the average annual rate of growth in national income (Onah, 2010).

Emphasis has however shifted from measuring development in terms of national incomes and growth (national economy) to the general well-being of man. This is because a country might experience growth in its national economy without an attendant change in the well-being of its people. There is a great leap in economic growth in China and India over some years now but that has not changed the massive poverty affecting a greater majority of their people (Onah, 2010). Again, citizens of South Africa presently in recession have better living condition than Nigerians with its country as the leading economy in Africa. Consequently, Onah (2010) explained that the new concepts of development are thus characterized by relatively: less concern with the quantity of production or output, material needs or monetary environment. This is reflected in dissatisfaction with the use of indicators such as per capital income or the rate of growth of national income as targets or measures of development and a corresponding search for alternative or additional indicators, such as life expectancy, access to various social or public services, freedom of speech, the degree of popular participation in government or decision making, or environmental conservation.

Development also is to lead long and healthy lives, to be knowledgeable, to have access to the resources needed for a decent standard of living and to be able to participate in the life of the community. It is also about freeing people from obstacles that affect their ability to develop their own lives and communities. Development, therefore, is empowerment: It is about local people taking control of their own lives, expressing their own demands and finding their own solutions to their problems (UNDP, 2008). Quoting Todaro, Nnamani (2009) asserts that development will

be said to have been attained if the core values of development are met. Core values imply elevation or upliftment of the whole society and social system to a good life.

Sustainable Development

The concept of sustainable development is coming in the heels of development which has been described as attaining the quality to life for all. Klarin (2018) wrote that quality of life for citizens can only be assured if there is more rational and efficient management of resources in the world that will ensure survival of future generations. In that regard, the key element of sustainable development is enhancement of life that is geared towards the future generation. In that perspective, United Nations Development Program (UNDP, 2009) conceives sustainable development as development that meets our present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Three elements were identified by UNDP (2009) which should work together to ensure sustainable development. These include economic development, social development and environmental protection. Klarin (2018) calls them triple bottom line concept-environmental sustainability, social sustainability and economic sustainability. Environmental sustainability focused on maintaining the quality of the environment which is necessary for conducting the economic activities and quality of life of people; social sustainability strives to ensure human rights and quality, preservation of cultural identity, respect for cultural diversity, race and religion; economic sustainability strives to maintain the natural, social and human capital required for income and living standard (Klarin, 2018, p. 68). Those three elements or pillars of development must be conceptualized together, planned together, implemented together and balance between them reached to achieve sustainable development (Klarin, 2018). Anazodo et al (2014) contend that sustainable development can only make sense to people when they are involved in the process. Ake (2001) submits that popular participation is crucial to sustainable development and is seen as the active involvement of all categories of civil servants in the process of setting goals and making decisions about involvement in the process not just the acceptability of end results which satisfies the need to participate. Ake (2001) notes that for sustainable development to be achieved there is need for human capacity building.

Emas (2015) opines that sustainable development aims to maintain economic advancement and progress while protecting the long-term value of the environment. Quoting UNDP, Emas (2015) contends that it provides a framework for the integration of environmental policies and development strategies. The interdependence between environmental stability and the economy is the foundation of sustainable development (Porter & Van der Linde, 1995). Sustainable development seeks to tackle the sources of environmental degrading opportunities and creating incentives for economic advancement (Porter & Van der Linde, 1995).

Sustainable development ensures according to Emas (2015) healthy environment such as clean air and water. This is only achievable through the integration and acknowledgement of economic, environmental and social concerns throughout the decision-making process. In the application of sustainable development theory, one issue comes to mind: Substitutability of capital (Stoddart, 2011). The author explains that there are several types of capital: Social, natural, and man-made. The idea of weak sustainable development explains that only the aggregate level of capital matters: Man-made or manufacturing capital is an adequate alternative to natural capital. Strong sustainability idea on the other hand, recognizes the unique features of natural resources that cannot be replaced by manufactured capital (Stoddart, 2011).

Contained within the definition of sustainable development is intergenerational equity. Dernbach (1998) Stoddart (2011) agree that intergenerational equity recognizes the long-term scale of sustainability in order to address the needs of future generations. The key principle of sustainable development is the integration of environmental, social and economic concerns into decision making by the authorities (Stoddart, 2011). In that light, sustainable development requires the integration of economic, environmental and social objective across sectors, territories and generations. Therefore, "sustainable development requires the elimination of fragmentation, that is, environmental, social and economic concerns must be integrated throughout decision making process in order to move towards development that is truly sustainable" (Emas, 2015, p.3).

Challenges Confronting SDGs 8 & 9 in Nigeria

Sustainable Development Goals were a development framework of the United Nations adopted in 2015 to replace the failed Millennium Development Goals which were hitherto being implemented by developing countries of the world. This new initiative of the United Nations is geared towards accelerating development in the third world countries. Unlike the Millennium Development Goals which was fundamentally left for the public sector, the SDGs have adopted an all-inclusive approach and cooperation between the public and private sector organizations in the execution of its goals (Jaiyesimi, 2016). However, the scheme is and will further be confronted by a quartet of challenges which include insecurity in the country, incidence of corona virus pandemic, insufficient funding and

corruption. Insecurity in Nigeria has taken a frightening proportion. The country is grappling with insurgency in the North East of the country, banditry in the North West, Fulani Herders massacre of farmers and other innocent citizens in virtually all corners of the country but most especially in the North Central, kidnapping across the country, agitations for autonomy by separatist group Indigenous peoples of Biafra (IPOB) in the Eastern Nigeria, incidence of unknown gun men attacking security posts in the South East and South South, etc. Insecurity according to Obarisiagbon and Akintoye (2019) has assumed an alarming rate affecting every facet of Nigerian life. Shettima (2012) in Ozor and Dinwobi(2018)opined that insecurity has brought about indiscriminate destruction of lives and properties, the dislocation of the local economy with serious implications for the living conditions of the inhabitants. Nigeria has experienced as an effect of insecurity in the country colossal destruction of infrastructure, properties, valuable human lives and economic sabotage that lead to the displacement of foreign direct investment and dislocation of the economy (Osemwegie, 2012 in Granville, 2020). Under these scenarios, no social or economic activities including activation of SDGs can thrive. That has been the dilemma facing the scheme. On the other hand, in a bid to curtail the grave insecurity situation in the country, federal government over the last decade had spent billions of dollars in procuring security equipment for its security agencies. An investigation by Abiodun et al (2020) discovered that Nigerian government has improved tremendously the budgetary allocations to the defense or military institutions in the last one decade although there are still persistent or unending insecurity in the state because of factors like corruption in the security sector, unhealthy rivalry among the military forces, poor leadership and absence of good governance (Abiodun et al, 2020) and I may add injustice being shown to some sections of the country.

Table 1
Military (Defense) Budget in Nigeria (2010-2019)

Year	Amount US Dollars (\$) Billions	Percentage (%) in Gross Domestic Product (GDP)
2010	1.99	0.54%
2011	2.38	0.58%
2012	2.32	0.50%
2013	2.42	0.47%
2014	2.36	0.41%
2015	2.07	0.42%
2016	1.72	0.43%
2017	1.62	0.43%
2018	2.04	0.51%
2019	1.86	0.44%

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria and Ministry of Defense, Abuja, Nigeria.

These huge amounts of funds could have gone into other aspects of national development including funding SDGs. In that regard, insecurity is sapping away funds meant for development of the country and thus a major headache in the polity. Achieving SDGs by 2030 will also be affected by the incidence of Covid-19 which has affected virtually all countries of the world. Covid-19 was declared a public health concern by WHO on January 30, 2020 (WHO, 2020). It has brought about recession in many countries' economies due to lock downs and other measures put up by various governments to curtail its incidence. Every government including that of Nigeria is giving priority to the pandemic to the extent in the views of Ekwebelem et al (2021) that some SDGs are being neglected or sacrificed to achieve control of the pandemic. In that regard, achieving SDGs 8 & 9 and indeed all the other goals of the scheme is threatened.

Table 2 captures it succinctly.

Table 2
Threatened Sustainable Development Goals in Africa

SDG	Status
SDG 1: No Poverty	Threatened
SDG 2: Zero hunger	Threatened
SDG 3: Good health and well-being	Threatened
SDG 4: Quality Education	Threatened
SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation	Threatened
SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth	Threatened

SDG 10: Reduced inequities	Threatened
SDG 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions	Threatened
SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals	Threatened

Source: Ekwebelem et al (2021)

In the light of the above, many analysts believe that it is impossible for SDGs to be met within the scheduled time of 2015-2023 because of the incidence of Corona Virus Pandemic (Ekwebelem et al, 2021; Heggen et al, 2020; Naidoo& Fisher, 2020; Filho et al, 2020). SDGs 8 & 9 are about promotion of sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all and; to build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation. These awesome goals cannot be met on or before 2030 target date because the funding needed to achieve them will be channeled to containing Corona virus pandemic. Instances abound. The Federal government of Nigeria released a five billion naira (US \$12.5million) special intervention fund to Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) and an additional ten billion naira (US \$25 million) to Lagos State, the epicenter of the outbreak in the first 100 days of 2020 (Amzat et al, 2020).

Ejiogu (2020) observed that Nigeria government went as far as borrowing to fund Covid-19 related economic and social interventions and that has squeezed the already bad economy further and has had a negative impact on businesses, employment, etc. Nobody knows when this pandemic will go away but until governments wrestle it successfully, full implementation of SDGs will be in abeyance. That Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is an initiative of the United Nations does not mean that the organization sponsors its implementation. Every participating country is responsible for its own implementation. It is a fact that massive amount of fund is needed to drive SDGs implementation and funding is virtually a handicap to the attainment of these goals in Africa especially Nigeria.

Nigeria is a country that depends mainly on oil rent as its main source of revenue. Unfortunately, the price of oil has remained low over the years and that has affected revenue generation of the country. Sayne and Hruby (2016) noted in this regard that there has been a rapid fall in world oil prices since July 2014 and that it threatens to undermine progress in the country. They noted further that the price of crude oil has been roughly halved, gutting government revenues, and reducing the country's GDP. With the world going green and laying more emphasis on cleaner energy, revenue from oil and other natural resources will continue to shrink. The effect of this as suggested by Ologunda et al (2020) is that many countries will record negative positions and might not be able to meet fiscal demands in the long run. The authors maintained that empirical results revealed that there was no long-term relationship between crude oil revenue (COR) and sustainable development. In other words, "any changes to COR have a potential negative effect on sustainable development (Ologunde et al, 2020, p.1).

This result is true of Nigeria. Nigeria's oil rent has dropped significantly and the little revenue trickling in is being competed for by various sectors of the economy. Every sector is being underfunded and feeling the effect adversely. 2020 health budget in Nigeria for instance stood at N25.5bn which is less than 5% of the annual budget of the country. This is against Africa Union (AU) recommendation of 15 percent of annual national budgets of Africa countries to health sector. The same situation is true of other sectors of the economy. This truism brings to fore the challenge of funding to the actualization of SDGs in Nigeria. Until government puts adequate funding into the scheme, the hope of realizing sustainable development goals by 2030 will be a mirage.

Another debilitating challenge of SDGs in Nigeria is corruption. Corruption is a major challenge to social, political and economic development in any country. The consequences of corruption are negative and unfavorable for the progress of any society (Igiebor, 2019). Transparency International (2005) postulates that corruption is one of the greatest challenges of the contemporary world which undermines good government, fundamentally distorts public policy, leads to the misallocation of resources, harms the private sector development and as well as hurts the poor. Corruption in Nigeria is rife and the major reason for the country's underdevelopment. Collaborating, Nwabueze (2020) wrote that in Nigeria, corruption is one of the numerous challenges that has significantly impeded the nations development. It is a major obstacle and roadblock to the transformation of the Nigerian economy. It is a socio-economic state where state resources that are intended for the country's advancement are diverted and used for private projects and programs (Nwabueze, 2020).

Corruption manifests itself in Nigeria in form of abuse of positions and privileges, low levels of transparency and accountability, inflation of contracts, bribery/kickbacks, misappropriation or diversion of funds, under and over-invoicing, etc. (Goodling, 2003). Nigeria's Information Minister went public with the fact that fifty-five people who were government ministers, state governors, public officials, bankers and businessmen stole 1.34 trillion naira (\$6.8billion) from Nigeria's public purse over a seven-year period (Sotunde, 2016). With this kind of malfeasance, no country can move forward.

In Nigeria, every citizen looks forward for an opportunity to get into government and into control of any form of funds to kick start the innate norm. Corruption is now a culture in Nigeria that is celebrated. People who succeed in

getting into positions of authority are celebrated by friends, family, well-wishers and even strangers. They are seen as having a blank cheque to loot the economy. With this mindset, it is feared that operators of SDGs in Nigeria will pounce on the meager funds provided by the government to run the scheme. Evidence abound that corruption is one of the factors that brought about the failure of Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in Nigeria (Okarafor&Anuforo, 2012; Tella, Liberty &Doho, 2014; Oleribe& Taylor-Robinson, 2016; Bamidele, Joseph &Oresajo, 2013). In an empirical review of the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria, Onimisi (2021) asserts that the implementation of sustainable development goals in Nigeria has been a daunting task for the government, policy makers and the citizenry due to corruption. The author maintained that corruption has denied the citizens the basic means of livelihood, with a worsening level of unemployment and has eroded almost all available goals of sustainable development and the policy strategies inherent in it (Onimisi, 2021). In that perspective, the objectives of SDG 8 which borders on promoting sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, that will bring about full and productive employment and decent work for all and SDG 9 which dwells on building resilient infrastructure, promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialization and fostering innovation are not being met due to the malaise of corruption. Ogbeyidi (2012) sums it up by asserting that corruption in Nigeria remains the biggest hindrance to the implementation of sustainable development.

Policy Options of Nigeria Government

More than ever before, Nigeria is in dire need of policies that will turn around the negative socio-economic indices being attributed to the country. For instance, Nigeria is said to be the poverty capital of the world (Borgen, 2020). Bloomberg (2021) published that Nigeria is to emerge as the nation with the highest unemployment rate on Earth, at just over 33%. How did Nigeria get this low and to this level of their present unemployment rate? According to Abubakar (2021) we got here by abandoning the people-centered leadership and free trade and deregulatory policies of the Obasanjo administration years (which saw us maintain an almost single-digit unemployment rate) and implementing discredit command and control policies that have led to massive capital flight from Nigeria. And with the paucity of funds, we continue to ramp up government involvement in sectors that ought to be left to the private sector, with the latest being the ill-advised \$1.5billion so-called rehabilitation of the Port-Harcourt Refinery that has failed to turn a profit for years (Abubakar, 2021).

Regarding the issue of chronic unemployment in Nigeria, an accelerated means to bring down the world record unemployment rate is via the policy of what Abubakar (2021) called incentive education. According to him, an educated citizenry is more employable and more self-employable. This incentive education can be done through enrolling 13.5 million out of school children in schools. By doing so, Nigeria could turn the corner in one generation. If not, the floodgates of unemployment will be further opened in the years to come (Abubakar, 2021).

Nigeria with its abundant natural resources would have been one of the richest nations of the world but for corruption. Many laudable initiatives like the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) that would have lifted the country out of poverty failed woefully due to corruption. Borgen (2020) attributed corruption as the major reason why poverty is in a very high state in Nigeria. Corruption according to Borgen (2020) is the single greatest obstacle that prevents Nigeria from prospering. In that essence, the government needs to come up with serious and stringent policies that will for once seriously tackle the menace of corruption. The policy recommended by this paper is that of establishing an independent court or tribunal solely for corruption cases that will be fast and swift in tackling cases of corruption. A situation where a corruption case lasts for decades with the accused roaming the streets free and some of them vying and winning elections and getting into further positions of authority does not augur well for the polity. Furthermore, more stringent laws that will map out stiffer punishments for culprits of corruption should be enacted by the legislature. Only these set of stiffer punishments will deter citizens from engaging in corruption. With less corruption, money will be freed for better funding and implementation of SDGs and other development initiatives of the government. A policy geared towards mapping out 26% of Nigeria's annual budget to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) will be appropriate for accelerated development. With this kind of policy, funding will be available and adequate to meet the goals of SDGs especially Goals 8 & 9 that hampers on creation of employment and provision of infrastructure. With adequate employment, poverty level will drastically reduce in the country. There will be savings and investments and growth in all economic indices. With availability of infrastructure, socio-economic activities will come back to normal. We will once again have a healthy and vibrant society. A policy on security also needs to be addressed. The level of insecurity in Nigeria is alarming. This paper supports the establishment of community policing, state police and vigilante groups as state policies that can tackle the spate of insecurities in Nigeria. Development programmes and projects can only be achieved in a serene and secured environment. Only pro-active security policies can ensure such environment.

Conclusion

Since the turn of this century, Nigeria has embarked on various development schemes. There had been interventions like the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), State Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (SEEDS), Privatization, Vision 2020, ERGP, MDGs, etc (Okonjo-Iweala&Osafo-Kwaako, 2007; Ministry of Budget & National Planning, 2020). All have been failures due largely to corruption, insecurity, poor funding, poor implementation, etc. Presently in Nigeria, poverty rate is at a critical level brought about mainly by chronic unemployment situation. Opportunities in SDGs are once again thrust on the country to create a sustainable economic growth. In doing that, it is important in the views of Okonjo-Iweala&Osafo-Kwaako (2007) to increase the quantity and quality of the government's infrastructure spending. Nigeria's state of infrastructure is remarkably very low. Okonjo-Iweala&Osafo-Kwaako (2007) estimates that a minimum of US \$5 billion a year for the next 10 years is needed to maintain and expand all types of infrastructure. Adequate infrastructure will bring about adequate employment leading to economic growth and sustainable development. By so doing, sustainable development goals will be met especially SDGs 8 & 9.

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